

Supplemental Material to AAPM Task Group Report 305: Proposed IHE Profile

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The co-Chairs of Task Group 305 have reviewed the required Conflict of Interest statement on file for each member of TG305 and determined that disclosure of potential Conflicts of Interest is

an adequate management plan. Disclosures of potential Conflicts of Interest for each member of TG305 are found at the close of this document.

This document is supplemental to AAPM Task Group Report 305, which was published in the Journal of Applied Clinical Medical Physics (DOI: [10.1002/acm2.13938](https://doi.org/10.1002/acm2.13938)). Please see the published report for definitions and additional commentary.

Proposed IHE Profile

An alternative to reject logs would be to use a workflow similar to the one defined in the IHE Profile “Radiation Exposure Monitoring (REM)” where information related to quality analysis (radiation dose data in the case of REM) is automatically transmitted from modalities to a central archive for analysis. IHE REM is a Final Text profile that is almost universally supported by CT devices and increasingly by other x-ray based modalities. This has engendered a marketplace of analysis software for the data.

In the case of reject analysis, the profile would likely also include the Rejection Note (in the form of a DICOM Key Object Selection file) that was introduced by the “Imaging Object Change Management (IOCM)” profile.¹ This IHE Profile, which is in “Trial Implementation” status at the time of this report, includes a process for a system to identify DICOM objects that have been rejected due to quality reasons.

In this supplemental material, we outline a new IHE Profile that combines the workflow and dataflow of IHE REM with the Rejection Note mechanism of IHE IOCM. This outline is meant to be a starting point for the further development of the profile. Similar to the IOCM framework, a technologist would be able to reject an image through the creation of a “Rejection Note,” which would be in the form of a DICOM Key Object Selection Document (KOS). The modality or PACS (or similar) would create the Rejection Note when the acquisition was rejected and include a reject reason in the KOS.

Using this workflow, the number of rejects and their reject reasons would be obtained by retrieving KOS objects from storage or by forwarding these objects to a separate tracking system, similar to those used to track patient radiation doses. The original rejected acquisition images would also be sent to a separate system or stored in a separate storage folder for later review. The IOCM profile describes PACS behaviors whereby images referenced from a Rejection Note could be sequestered from the radiology reporting process, but still be made available for review as part of quality analysis.

The denominator of the reject rate would need to be similarly tracked. This could either be through a query of all images in a study (rejected and accepted) for a parameter such as acquisition time, through the use of the DICOM structured report (which should have the number of acquisitions at the time the study is closed on the modality, although not necessarily an individual identification of acquisitions), or by sending all acquisitions to a separate tracking system or PACS reject module, which could use DICOM identifiers such as acquisition time, irradiation event ID, or other image properties to identify each acquisition. The number of rejected images from Key Object Selection Documents and the total number of acquisitions could then be used to identify a reject rate for a given technologist, exam protocol, system, etc. If necessary, a data feed from the RIS could be used for technologist identification.

Ideally, this method would be implemented both on acquisition workstations and on the PACS, allowing rejects to be initiated at either location. However, this would require upgrading both the acquisition workstations and PACS. This method could be implemented using an upgraded PACS alone if the site modified their workflow to only reject within PACS.

Reject Analysis – Brief Proposal to IHE

Contents [\[hide\]](#)

- 1 1. Proposed Workitem: Reject Analysis (XRA) Profile
- 2 2. The Problem
- 3 3. Key Use Case
- 4 4. Standards and Systems
 - 4.1 Standards
- 5 5. Discussion
 - 5.1 Risks

1. Proposed Workitem: Reject Analysis (XRA) Profile

- Proposal Editor:
- Editor:
- Domain: Radiology

2. The Problem

The acquisition of radiographs is a technical process and variations in a variety of details (patient positioning, imaging technique, equipment performance) can yield non-diagnostic results.

Site QA processes, of which reject analysis is a part, are an ongoing effort to maintain and improve imaging quality in the face of these challenges.

The conventional approach is for each x-ray device to keep local logs and copies of images, requiring site staff to schedule regular visits to each x-ray device. The log format, content, and level of detail are not standardized, nor is the GUI or method for accessing the information. Some devices internally summarize the data. It is often useful to review the images to understand the nature of the defect and its source. Some devices store full fidelity copies of problem images, others store reduced resolution or quality, and others store none at all.

All this makes it an enormous challenge to operate QA as an enterprise-level program with uniform quality standards, rather than a replicated series of device-level programs, not to mention the inherent inefficiencies of repeating work differently at many different devices.

3. Key Use Case

Goal: Capture details of x-ray acquisitions and the results of QA steps to facilitate the later analysis of “rejects” (images that were non-diagnostic or at least sub-par in some way) to understand and improve.

Current workflow:

- Modalities record some reject details in internal log files.
- Staff periodically visit each acquisition device.
 - Each acquisition model has a different GUI and method for accessing the log files.
 - Each vendors log file has different content and format.
 - Some allow the log to be exported in Excel or XML or as a text file.
 - Some do their own analysis and provide a report in some format.
 - Some keep reduced versions of rejected images as jpegs.
- Staff manually combine all the different logs and reports, and find some way to summarize.

Proposed workflow (similar to REM):

- When an image is flagged as a problem on the Modality, it stores a KOS Rejection Note to the PACS study.
- Modalities are configured to either store rejected DICOM images to PACS or a configured alternate location.
 - If the PACS understands KOS Rejection Notes, it will sequester the rejected images from clinical use, otherwise the images will need to be sent to an alternate location.
- Modalities store dose objects as described in the REM profile.
- When an image is flagged as a problem on a QA station, it stores a KOS Rejection Note to the PACS study.
- Staff periodically visit a single reject analysis workstation/package.
 - The Reject Analysis retrieves all KOS along with the associated dose reports and images
 - The Reject Analysis prepares customizable reports.

- Standardized reject codes would facilitate easier cross device and cross hospital analysis..

4. Standards and Systems

Modalities – the initial focus would be strongly around radiography but could apply to any modality

Storage - PACS, VNA, etc.

Reject Analyzers - like REM Dose Information Reporters (same system?)

Registry - like REM Dose Registries

Standards

- AAPM TG-305 Report – discussion of requirements
- IHE REM – provides the overall model
- DICOM KOS (IOCM Rejection Note)
- DICOM RDSR
- DICOM Image IODs
- HL7, if necessary, to identify the technologist performing an exam.

5. Discussion

This would mostly be a clone of the IHE REM profile with an added payload of IOCM rejection notes.

Depending on the situation, QA reviewers would look at detailed or summary information and might consult the rejection notes, the associated dose reports, and the rejected images themselves.

Disclosure Statement

1. The members of TG305 listed below attest that they have no potential Conflicts of Interest related to the subject matter or materials presented in this document.

Ingrid Reiser, Ryan Fisher, Katie Hulme, Mary Ellen Jafari, Emily Marshall, Quentin Moore, Nicole Murphy, Thomas Nishino, Adrian Sanchez, William Sensakovic, Lawrence Tarbox, Alisa Walz-Flannigan, and Jie Zhang.

2. The members of TG305 listed below disclose the following potential Conflict(s) of Interest related to subject matter or materials presented in this document.

During the time this work was performed, Kevin Little was an employee of Ohio State University, which has research agreements with Qaelum NV and Siemens Healthineers. Bruce Apgar is an

employee of AGFA HealthCare. Jaydev Dave has received research support from Philips Healthcare, Lantheus Medical Imaging Inc., and GE Healthcare. Stephen Meyer is an employee of Canon Medical Components USA. Kevin O'Donnell is an employee of Canon Medical Research USA, a subsidiary of Canon Medical Systems Corporation. Katelyn Nye is an employee of GE Healthcare. Dalal Poonam is an employee of GE Healthcare. During part of the time this work was performed, John Sabol was an employee of GE Healthcare, Robert Uzenoff was an employee of Fujifilm Medical Systems U.S.A., and Charles Willis was a member of the GE Medical Advisory Board for Radiography.

References

1. Imaging Object Change Management. Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise. Published June 2018. Accessed May 7, 2020. https://wiki.ihe.net/index.php/Imaging_Object_Change_Management